

Group-contribution method for the estimation of surface tension of binary liquid mixtures

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Manuscript received 10 May 2007, revised 8 October 2007, accepted 28 May 2008

Abstract : Corresponding-states group-contributions method (CSGC), for the first time, has been extended to estimate surface tension of five binary liquid mixtures namely, 1,4-dioxane + hexane, 1,4-dioxane + heptane, 1,4-dioxane + octane, 1,4-dioxane + nonane, 1,4-dioxane + decane. Computed values of the employed method are compared with the experimental findings. The agreement between experimental and theoretical values is found to be satisfactory.

Keywords : Surface tension, group-contributions, corresponding-states, liquid mixtures, binary mixtures.

Introduction

One of the most striking demonstrations of the intermolecular forces is the tension at the surface of a liquid. Surface tension provides information about the structure and energy interactions in the liquid-vapour interface, and is a property of great importance in mass transfer processes such as distillation, extraction or absorption. Surface tension data are also useful in environmental engineering and biotechnology. Experimental surface tension data for binary liquid mixtures are reported by several workers¹⁻⁴. Various empirical and semi-empirical methods⁵⁻⁷ have been developed for the estimation of surface tension of binary liquid mixtures. Most of such methods have certain limitations and are not of general validity. There is a need to have a simple and reliable method for the estimation of surface tension of liquid mixtures, based on the easily available experimental data of physical properties like density, boiling point, critical constants etc. of pure liquid component. Lu *et al.*⁸ developed a semi-empirical model for calculating surface tension of pure liquids and binary mixtures so that correlation used in this method could further be used for predicting surface tension of multicomponent liquid mixtures. Recently⁸, a new estimative method, namely, corresponding-states group-contribution method was proposed for

estimating the surface tension of pure liquids. This approach is a modification of widely used Brock-Bird relation^{6,9} which is based on the corresponding-states principle involving only the values of critical constants and density for calculating the surface tension of pure non-polar liquids. The modification involves the application of group-contributions in the Brock-Bird relation. The modified equation is known as corresponding-states group-contributions (CSGC) method. In the present work we have extended this CSGC method to the binary liquid mixtures. This new approach has been applied to five binary liquid mixtures for the calculation of surface tension, the experimental values of which are taken from literature¹⁰⁻¹². Five binary mixtures considered for the present study are : 1,4-dioxane + hexane, 1,4-dioxane + heptane, 1,4-dioxane + octane, 1,4-dioxane + nonane, 1,4-dioxane + decane.

Theoretical :

Based on the corresponding-states principle, Brock and Bird^{6,9} relation (1) has been found to be the excellent method for the estimation of surface tension (σ) of pure liquids⁶. This equation is given by

$$\frac{\sigma}{P_c^{2/3} T_c^{1/3}} = (0.132\alpha_c - 0.279)(1 - T_r)^{11/9} \quad (1)$$

where α_c is the Riedel parameter¹³ at the critical point. Here α_c is defined as $d \ln P_{vap}/d \ln T_r$. Further, Miller¹⁴ related α_c to T_{br} and P_c ,

$$\alpha_c = 0.9076 \left(1 + \frac{T_{br} \ln (P_c / 1.01325)}{1 - T_{br}} \right) \quad (2)$$

From the above relation, it can be shown that

$$\sigma = P_c^{2/3} T_c^{1/3} Q(1 - T_r)^{11/9} \quad (3)$$

$$Q = 0.1196 \left[1 + \frac{T_{br} \ln (P_c / 1.01325)}{1 - T_{br}} \right] - 0.279 \quad (4)$$

These equations, vide (3) and (4), were satisfactorily used to estimate σ for non-polar pure liquids⁶. The original Brock-Bird eq. (1) has been extended to liquid mixtures^{7,15-17} (binary and higher order). Very recently Li *et al.*⁸ proposed a new equation by applying the corresponding-states group-contribution method to Brock-Bird equation and the obtained equation is similar to Brock-Bird and Miller :

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{P_c^*}{101.325} \right)^a (T_c^*)^b (c\alpha_c - d)(1 - T_r^*)^e$$

where

$$\alpha_{c_i} = f \left(1 + \frac{T_{br_i}^* \ln (P_{c_i}^* / 101.325)}{1 - T_{br_i}^*} \right)$$

$$T_r^* = \frac{T}{T_c^*}$$

$$T_{br}^* = \frac{T_b}{T_c^*}$$

In the above equation T_b is the normal boiling point of liquid, T_c^* and P_c^* are the assumed-critical temperature and assumed-critical pressure respectively, which are obtained from the following group-contribution equations⁸

$$T_c^* = \frac{T_b}{\left[A_T + B_T \left(\sum_i^M n_i \Delta_{T_i} \right) + C_T \left(\sum_i^M n_i \Delta_{T_i} \right)^2 + D_T \left(\sum_i^M n_i \Delta_{T_i} \right)^3 \right]} \quad (6)$$

$$P_c^* = \frac{101.325 \ln (T_b - 273.15)}{\left[A_p + B_p \left(\sum_i^M n_i \Delta_{p_i} \right) + C_p \left(\sum_i^M n_i \Delta_{p_i} \right)^2 + D_p \left(\sum_i^M n_i \Delta_{p_i} \right)^3 \right]} \quad (7)$$

where Δ_{T_i} and Δ_{p_i} are the contribution values of group i to the assumed-critical temperature T_c^* and the assumed-critical pressure. The experimental surface tension data of pure liquids are used to obtain the values of constants $A_T \sim D_T$ and $A_p \sim D_p$, as well as of a, b, c, d, e and f of above equations. These equations have been applied to pure liquids only (polar and non-polar) with wide-range of applicability.

In the present work, an attempt has been made to extend corresponding-states group-contribution method, vide eqs. (5)-(7), to the binary liquid mixtures, which has not, so far, been done, as far as our knowledge is concerned. By applying the additivity rules for all the parameters involved in the above equations, as have been done earlier^{7,15-17}, the following expressions are obtained for estimating the surface tension of binary liquid mixtures from corresponding-states group-contribution (CSGC) method :

$$\sigma_m = \left(\frac{\sum_i^M x_i P_c^*}{101.325} \right)^a \left(\sum_i^M x_i T_c^* \right)^b \left(c \sum_i^M x_i \alpha_c - d \right) \left(1 - \sum_i^M x_i T_c^* \right)^e \quad (8)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction of i -th component in the mixture, T_c^* and P_c^* are given by eqs. (6) and (7) respectively. α_c is obtained from eq. (5).

Results and discussion

Five binary mixtures viz. 1,4-dioxane + hexane, 1,4-dioxane + heptane, 1,4-dioxane + octane, 1,4-dioxane + nonane, 1,4-dioxane + decane have been considered in the present investigation. Experimental data of pure

components and mixtures are taken from the literature¹⁰⁻¹². In the present work, corresponding-state group-contribution method for estimating surface tension of liquids is extended for binary liquid mixtures. In this method, we require only boiling point of pure components, which are taken from the literature¹², and are recorded in Table 1. Assumed-critical pressure (P_c^*) and assumed-critical temperature (T_c^*) of components are cal-

Table 1. Boiling point of pure components

Components	Boiling point (K)
1,4-Dioxane	374.6
Pentane	309.1
Hexane	341.8
Heptane	371.6
Octane	398.7
Nonane	423.9
Decane	447.2
Benzene	353.1
Cyclohexane	353.8
Toluene	383.7
2,2,4-Trimethyl pentane	372.3

culated by the method of group-contribution⁸. These computed values have been then used to evaluate surface tension of systems under the present consideration. The calculated and experimental values of surface tension are plotted against mole fraction of the first component, and are depicted in Figs. 1 to 5 for binary and ternary systems. Fig. 1 represents the comparison between theoretical and experimental values of surface tension for all the binary mixtures under consideration.

Fig. 1. Variation of experimental and theoretical values of surface tension for five binary mixtures (I) 1,4-dioxane + hexane, (II) 1,4-dioxane + heptane, (III) 1,4-dioxane + octane, (IV) 1,4-dioxane + nonane and (V) 1,4-dioxane + decane with varying composition of 1,4-dioxane (x_1): (□) Expt., (△) group contribution method.

Fig. 2. Variation of experimental and theoretical values of surface tension for ternary mixture : *n*-pentane + *n*-hexane + benzene : (□) Expt., (△) group contribution method.

Fig. 3. Variation of experimental and theoretical values of surface tension for ternary mixture : cyclohexane + *n*-heptane + toluene : (□) Expt., (△) group contribution method.

Fig. 4. Variation of experimental and theoretical values of surface tension for ternary mixture : 2,2,4-TMP + cyclohexane + decane : (□) Expt., (△) group contribution method.

Fig. 5. Variation of experimental and theoretical values of surface tension for ternary mixture : benzene + *n*-hexane + cyclohexane : (□) Expt., (△) group contribution method.

Surface tension values of *n*-alkanes are lower than that of 1,4-dioxane but increase with chain length due to increasing strength of dispersion forces. In the case of binary liquid mixtures under investigation, surface tension, once again, increases with increase in chain length of the second component (alkanes). Furthermore, it is evident from Fig. 1 that computed values of the surface tension generally deviate more in 1,4-dioxane enriched region. It may be due to some special behaviour of liquid mixtures. Curves are skewed towards the dioxane rich mole fraction region. *n*-Alkanes forms random coils owing to internal rotation about C-C bonds, and this tendency increases with increase in chain length. For cyclic ether + alkane mixture, lower surface tension of alkanes and efficiency of dipole-dipole interaction in liquid phase rather in the interface force the cyclic ether to avoid the interface. Therefore, the alkane molecules are expelled from the bulk to the interface due to the attractive force between molecules of 1,4-dioxane.

Thus, we see that the present approach of estimating theoretically surface tension of binary liquid mixture is quite satisfactory. The beauty of the employed method is that it needs only the knowledge of boiling point and structural feature of contributory components to evaluate surface tension of liquid mixtures. The method does not require any property of liquid mixture except only the

boiling point and critical constants of pure components of binary mixtures.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors NKS is thankful to CSIR, New Delhi, India, for the financial support. We are also grateful to Prof. J. D. Pandey, Former Head and UGC Emeritus Fellow for the valuable suggestions.

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